

ECONOMIC CONTENT OF THE LAND MARKET

Ubaydov Mirshod Ismailovich

Chief Specialist of the State Asset Management Agency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828026>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the scientific justification of economic concepts such as the concept of the land market, its content and value, its functions.

Key words: land, market, mechanism, economy, distribution, investment, resource.

Introduction. The satisfaction of rapidly growing needs in our society and economy, in turn, requires the rational and efficient use of land resources. Indeed, today there are many problems associated with the management of land resources in the world. In particular, these include the activation of land redistribution, the reduction of land productivity and the lack of investments, the non-availability of economic methods for managing land degradation, and the Prevention of agricultural land losses [1].

In the field of improving the regulatory framework of land reform, it is necessary to carry out the following measures:

- completion of territorial zoning of the lands of settlements and other territories in order to establish urban planning rules for the permitted use of real estate;
- completion of the process of establishing the boundaries of Republican subjects and district lands in places;
- construction of land as an information base and the creation of a cadastre of urban planning documents;
- rights to real estate and transactions with it improvement of the state registration system;
- creation of a register of vacant land for the development of industry in areas provided with relevant production infrastructure – transport communications, gas, drinking water and heat supply, within the framework of information interaction with the state land cadastre and land formation cadastre and urban planning documents; power supply, communication;
- simplify the granting of rights to land plots for the implementation of investment projects;
- to note in the legislation the legal concept of a single real estate object, which provides for the registration of property rights to the land plot and the buildings (structures) located on it at the same time;

- ensure a consistent transition to providing land plots in a largely competitive manner with initial registration on property or as an object of long-term leased real estate in order to create the possibility of crediting the future construction under the Pledge of a land plot;

- completion of the process of transferring ownership of land plots on state or municipal property to the owners of real estate located in them; development of mechanisms for paying the owner-enterprises in installments in the purchase of land plots in order to reduce the amount of their own funds allocated for the purchase of enterprises;

- Organization of effective control over the protection and use of land resources aimed at preserving and restoring the natural properties of the land;

- creation of mechanisms for the implementation of the client's rights to ensure the possibility of accounting for property with minimal costs [2].

In the field of improving state regulation of the real estate market, it is necessary to carry out the following measures:

- legislative determination of complex subjects, deadlines for their implementation by each type of state examination of project documentation;

- exclusion of the function of disposal of land and real estate from the powers of various agencies, in addition to the fact that the state is represented as an owner;

- simplify the procedure and ensure equal access of small business entities in auctions for the sale of state and municipal real estate objects [3].

The most important indicators of state success in the development of the real estate market are the reduction in the time and costs of making real estate transactions. Market infrastructure at the macroeconomic level ideas about the development of a market economy in society are formed in stages: first, the content of this concept is described, and then the situation is assessed, clarification of the possibilities of its transformation is introduced and, over time, an understanding of the selected infrastructure is given [4].

Market infrastructure is the link between production and consumption, and therefore it has a great impact on the economy. The concept is diverse and its essence can be defined as the sum of institutions, organizations, state and commercial enterprises that ensure the normal functioning of goods and other markets, the interaction and efficient service of producers and consumers. A developed market infrastructure allows you to quickly solve a temporary shortage of goods, since it helps to create an effective investment environment

and meet demand in the complex of Information, Services, Banking, Insurance and other services [5].

Ensuring the continuous functioning of economic relations and interaction between the subjects of the market economy is the regulation of the movement of commodity-cash flows, the subjects of the market economy, on the one hand, the owners of resources and the owners of products, on the other hand, commercial structures and the state.

The classifications of economic entities complement each other, and this differentiates entities according to different criteria. Each of the selected functions is characterized by certain functions or features. The supplying function is an internal function, which in its essence depends on the infrastructure of the economy, characterizing its essence and immediate purpose. This feature is passive, the market infrastructure as a subsystem of the entire economy provides conditions and opportunities for the market economy to perform economic functions (first of all, such as the optimal accumulation of resources and the creation of products of economic activity from them) without direct participation. It is the creation of a product, but this function can also be directly classified, since the formation of an adequate infrastructure is one of the immediate and indispensable conditions for the existence and reproduction of an economic system, as well as its development.

The regulatory function is next to the provider, its continuation, but its characteristics are different, directly opposite, first of all, external. Despite the fact that infrastructure is a subsystem of the economic system, this subsystem exists above the process of interaction between economic entities, without which, on the other hand, under certain conditions, it can have a very important effect on the entire execution process. In this role, this function is active, which is especially noticeable in countries with a transitional economy. Finally, by its nature, it is a function of opposite action, which directly signals the economy about certain problems in the field of product creation.

The two functions are closely related and cannot be implemented without each other. The result of their interaction is a well-defined synthetic effect, which can be defined as the optimization of the movement of commodity-cash flows. In the process of ensuring and regulating the movement of commodity-money flows, infrastructure helps to illuminate the correspondence between social needs for goods and services and the ability of the production process to satisfy them on the necessary scale. This ensures integration in the implementation of both functions, achieving proportionality in the allocation of

resources, which, in turn, leads to minimization of costs associated with the allocation of resources and products. Therefore, the infrastructure provides the efficiency of the economy according to its functions, as well as to the extent and mechanisms inherent in it. This part of efficiency can be called latent efficiency, since methods of comparing costs and benefits do not apply to it directly and indirectly.

Market infrastructure institutions are engaged in the provision of intermediary services in the field of investments, insurance of various aspects of economic activity and also carry out various operas that are important. infrastructure is also used in macroeconomic regulation: with its help, the state implements anti-inflation measures, employment policies, fights cyclical fluctuations in the economy. Infrastructure is designed to ensure the culturality of the activities of market participants, the elements of which are not burdened by external entities, but are formed by the market Relations themselves.

A market economy system is a system of allocation and utilization of resources through a market competition mechanism based on commodity price. It involves the creation of economic goods and their delivery to consumers. The latter requires the organization of the sphere of turnover. Market infrastructure is the sum of institutions that ensure the circulation of various goods. Ensuring the relationship between commodity producers and their direct consumers is the main goal of infrastructure institutions. For the normal functioning of the market economy, an infrastructure is of course necessary.

Conclusion. The mechanism of a market economy is complemented by state regulation of the economy. In terms of socio-economic relations, this system is dominated by private ownership of the means of production, but at the same time State, mixed and cooperative property plays an important role. Evaluating this system in terms of the level of material and technical development, it is possible to define a market economic system as an industrial and post-industrial economy.

References:

1. Abdurashid A., Muhammadbek M. Regulation of the Diversification of the Use of the District Land Fund through the General Scheme //Design Engineering. – 2021. – C. 2565-2581.
2. Altiev, A., & Mahsudov, M. (2020). Improvement of the regulation mechanisms of the land use diversification. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. ISSN, 9752366.

3. Sultanovich, A. A., & Ugli, M. M. D. (2019). Methods of forecasting and management of land fund diversification in local areas. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(3), 403-411.
4. Altiev, A. S., & Mahsudov, M. D. (2019). REPRODUCTION CYCLE OF LAND. *Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education*, 3(4), 96-102.
5. AR Babajanov, MD Mahsudov. Diversification of land fund in the district. Monograph. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing, 77-78

